

DAMAGE MONITORING DURING ISOTHERMAL CREEP OF MMC'S USING POISSON RATIO MEASUREMENT

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ABSTRACT

Isothermal creep tests have been performed on Al-based composites reinforced with either angular, spherical or short fibre alumina, or short carbon fibres. Laser scanning extensometry was used to monitor both axial and transverse strain during deformation, from which Poisson ratio values could be calculated. Local strain distributions were calculated from accurate specimen dimension measurements taken before and after testing. Variations in the Poisson ratio during deformation were used to characterise the evolution of damage and were correlated with microstructural observations.

INTRODUCTION

Experimental data[1] often indicate that the presence of particulate reinforcement reduces the steady state creep rate in MMCs. However, some such data are misleading, in that comparison is not being made with a matrix having the same microstructure. In particular, many Al-based MMCs have been made by a powder-route which leaves fine dispersions of alumina, from the surface oxide on the Al powder particles. These dispersoids raise the resistance to creep substantially by inhibition of dislocation motion. Most papers have neither specified the processing details which determine the dispersoid content, nor reported direct microstructural observations of these fine particles. Only a few authors[2] have clearly identified this problem. In fact, the presence of particulate reinforcement can impair the creep resistance of a dispersion-strengthened matrix. This is probably due to the promotion of cavitation, which both raises the apparent creep rate and accelerates final rupture. However, addition of short fibres usually gives a clear improvement in axial creep strength, presumably because effective load transfer to the fibres can take place. While damage processes in these composites have been characterised during tensile deformation at both room temperature[3,4] and elevated temperature[5,6], little work has been done on damage evolution during creep.

It has been confirmed[7] that creep resistance is raised by the presence of fibres, even in the absence of any dispersion strengthening. An obvious inference from data of this type is that optimal creep resistance might be obtained by incorporating both dispersoids to inhibit dislocation motion in the matrix, and fibres of reasonably high aspect ratio, to relieve the matrix of much of the applied load. However, there is little or no information available to indicate how void growth and coalescence processes are likely to be influenced by the presence of these constituents at elevated temperature. The present work is aimed at exploring damage development during isothermal creep.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

MATERIAL PRODUCTION

The composites were produced via either dry blending, followed by canning under vacuum and hot extrusion, or squeeze infiltration of Saffil preforms, followed by extrusion. For the powder route composites, the reinforcements used were spherical alumina (diameter ~10 μm), angular alumina (diameter ~13 μm), chopped "Saffil" alumina fibre and chopped carbon fibre, both with an approximate aspect ratio of 5. Commercial purity aluminium was used for the matrix in all cases. Details of the fabrication procedures can be found elsewhere[4]. The powder route material contained about 0.08 vol% of fine alumina platelets (diameter ~ 50 nm, thickness ~ 10 nm) derived from the oxide skin on the Al powder, broken up and aligned during extrusion.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Cylindrical specimens were machined from the extrudates, with flanges for monitoring of axial strain using a laser scanning extensometer[. This is a non-contact method, capable of measuring larger dimensional changes than strain gauges, with a precision better than 1 μm . Transverse strains were monitored in the same way, at a selected point along the gauge length. Tensile creep tests were carried out isothermally at 270°C with various static loads.

MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION

To measure the void content, specimen density was measured prior to and after failure using an Archimedean technique[3]. After testing, specimens were sectioned and examined via optical and scanning electron (SEM) microscopy. To observe the cavities and fine oxide particles in the SEM, electropolishing was used to minimise the surface damage during preparation. Details of specimen preparation and densitometry are given elsewhere[4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT SHAPE

None of the specimens showed a well-defined steady state creep regime. The minimum strain rate has therefore been taken to represent the creep resistance. These are plotted in Fig. 1 against the applied stress, for 20 vol% composites, together with creep rupture lifetimes. Material with spherical reinforcement showed the highest strain rates, while that with angular particles exhibited the lowest, with the fibre composites intermediate.

Axial creep curves for 20% spherical and angular particle composites are shown in Fig.2. The spherical reinforcement gave much the higher strain to failure. However, the creep rupture lifetime was lower with the spherical reinforcement. This effect is presumably due to the difference in reinforcement shape, or possibly to a change in reinforcement strength attributable to its processing history.

Figure 1. (a) Minimum creep strain rates and (b) time to failure, for 20 vol% powder-route composites tested with different loads at a temperature of 270°C.

This effect could be partly explained in terms of the load transfer. Since the angular particles have a slightly higher aspect ratio than the spherical, and become aligned during extrusion, they will carry more load, reducing the mean stresses in the matrix and hence lowering the creep rate. However, the lower creep resistance exhibited by the fibre-reinforced composites suggests that this is not a dominant effect. Damage formation should also be considered. Previous work[9] has established that an angular shape can promote cavitation, with void nucleation sites being where large hydrostatic stresses are generated. A key question is whether such cavitation impairs composite properties by promoting failure, or acts primarily as a stress relaxation mechanism, reducing the average matrix stresses and hence the driving force for creep. The latter is a possible explanation of the effect shown in Fig.2.

This explanation is consistent with microstructural observations. Fig.3 shows typical micrographs from angular and spherical material, taken at different points along the gauge length. In the spherical material, the cavitation observed is confined to the vicinity of the fracture surface. Near the fracture surface cavitation is extensive and is not associated with individual particles. This suggests that the onset of cavitation is catastrophic, leading to rapid failure. In the angular material, on the other hand, cavitation occurs throughout the gauge length, suggesting that the onset of cavitation is not catastrophic. In this case the

voids are associated with individual particles and occur at angularities. The void volume is relatively small, making their coalescence unlikely, so that failure is not accelerated by the damage. The final average void contents obtained from density measurements were 0.4% for the angular material, compared with 0.7% for the spherical.

For the fibre composites, the minimum strain rates were higher, and the rupture lifetimes lower, than for the angular material. This appears surprising, since the higher aspect ratios should enhance load transfer. The most probable explanation lies in the nature of the microstructures. The 20% Saffil composites showed appreciable reinforcement clustering, while the particles were more homogeneously distributed. Clustered regions were clearly preferred sites for damage development. This is illustrated by Fig.4, which shows a typical damaged region in fibre reinforced material. The high local matrix constraint in regions of clustered reinforcement prevent local plastic flow, thus promoting early damage. This results in large defects, which often become sites for failure initiation.

Figure 2. Axial creep curves for CP Al reinforced with 20 vol% spherical or angular alumina, with an applied stress of 40 MPa at 270°C.

Cavitation in the carbon fibre composites was higher than with the Saffil fibres. The interfacial bond strength between carbon fibre and aluminium is known to be lower than that for Saffil. The critical stress for damage initiation is expected to be lower for carbon fibres. While fibre clusters were preferred sites for damage with Saffil, debonding and void formation often occurred at individual fibre/matrix interfaces with carbon fibres. This effect is apparent in Fig.4.

The Poisson ratio can be used to characterise damage development[10,11]. If cavitation occurs in a part of the matrix shielded from lateral contraction, for instance adjacent to a reinforcement particle along the line of applied stress, a reduction in the instantaneous Poisson ratio is expected, since an axial strain can occur without the corresponding lateral contraction. This is confirmed by Fig.5, which shows the changing Poisson ratio during creep of composites with spherical alumina and carbon fibre. These data confirm the microstructural observations already made. A drop in Poisson ratio with the spherical reinforcement occurs only towards the end of the creep lifetime, confirming that the onset of damage leads rapidly to failure. For the carbon fibre composite, damage develops progressively throughout deformation. This suggests that cavitation occurs easily due to poor interfacial bonding, but that it is not catastrophic and significant cavity levels can be accommodated without leading rapidly to failure.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs from failed specimens with 20 vol% of (a) spherical Al_2O_3 and (b) angular Al_2O_3 , taken (i) near a fracture surface and (ii) near the end of the gauge length.

Figure 4. SEM micrograph showing typical damage regions in specimens with 20vol% of (a) Saffil and (b) carbon fibre, taken from near a fracture surface.

It should be noted that, since the axial strain is measured over the whole specimen, and the transverse at one point only, the onset of necking means that the value of the Poisson ratio measured in this way becomes unreliable. However, for all the cases described here, significant necking did not occur until very late in the creep lifetime.

Figure 5. Poisson Ratio plots as a function of the proportion of the lifetime expended, for 20 vol% carbon fibre and spherical alumina composites, tested at 270°C.

EFFECT OF MATRIX OXIDE CONTENT

Creep curves and corresponding Poisson ratio data are shown in Figs. 6 and 7 for 10 vol% Saffil, fabricated using a powder route or squeeze infiltration, followed by extrusion. The average fibre aspect ratio in all cases was about 5. The powder-route composite failed at lower strains and had a longer creep rupture lifetime than the infiltrated composite. This is due to the presence of the oxide particles in the matrix, along the prior particle boundaries of the aluminium, which are not present in the infiltrated material. The presence of a dispersion-strengthening constituent reduces the creep rate by providing barriers to dislocation motion. From Fig. 7, it can be seen that damage occurs earlier with the squeeze-infiltrated composite than with the powder-route material.

The squeeze-infiltrated material has a much higher failure strain than the powder-route composite. This can be explained by considering the microstructural sites for damage. The 10 vol% powder-route composite showed severe fibre clustering and these clusters were the favoured damage initiation sites. The 10 vol% infiltrated composite, however, had a far more homogeneous reinforcement distribution, and individual fibres often acted as void nucleation sites. These defects were thus significantly smaller, so that a greater extent of damage could be accommodated before failure. This is consistent with density measurements taken on failed specimens. For the three composites with clustered reinforcement (both 20 vol% specimens and the powder route 10 vol% material), the void content at failure was between 0.6 and 0.8%. The 10 vol% infiltrated composite, however contained about 2.0 % porosity at failure.

Figure 6. Axial and transverse creep curves for 10 vol% Saffil composites produced via powder or infiltration routes, for an applied stress of 30 MPa at 270°C.

Figure 7. Poisson ratio data for 10 vol% Saffil composites produced via powder or infiltration routes, for an applied stress of 30 MPa at 270°C.

CONCLUSIONS

Where cavitation occurs at isolated reinforcement particles, the resulting stress relaxation can reduce the creep rate, rather than accelerating composite failure. The presence of fine oxide dispersions in the matrix increases the time to failure. The strain to failure of the composites is sensitive to the preferred cavity nucleation sites, which in turn depend on the homogeneity of the reinforcement distribution. Clusters of reinforcement tend to cause premature creep rupture. Poisson ratio monitoring can be successfully used to characterise the damage evolution process.

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